

Hemisection: An Obstacle For Perio-endo Lesion

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Abstract

Hemisection is the treatment of choice when caries, perforation, root resorption or periodontal defect is restricted to one root while the other root is relatively healthy. It is a resection of periodontally involved root along with the associated crown portion. Hemisection denotes the removal of compromised root and its associated crown portion with the loss of periodontal attachment and to maintain the original tooth structure, surrounding alveolar bone and to attain the fixed prosthesis. Prognosis and treatment of perio-endo lesions depend on the severity of bone loss, root trunk length, degree of root separation, curvature of root, ability to eradicate the osseous or restorative defect and oral hygiene procedures. This case report demonstrates a procedure for hemisection in mandibular molar by vertical cut method, its subsequent restoration and successful management with occlusal rehabilitation. It was aimed to follow a conservative treatment approach to retain as much as original tooth structure possible against the conventional option of extracting the natural tooth. Hemisection and prosthetic rehabilitation yielded a long-term satisfactory result.

Keywords: Hemisection, Resorption, Prosthetic Rehabilitation.

Introduction

Advances in dental therapy have made it possible to keep teeth that were previously thought to be incurable. Patients now have the chance to maintain a functional dentition for the rest of their lives.

Such treatment approaches are multi-disciplinary in nature. One such therapeutic approach is hemisection, which incorporates concepts from prosthodontics, endodontics, periodontics and oral surgery.¹ The most important factor in deciding the long-term outcome in these situations is the proper case selection.

Hemisection refers to sectioning of a mandibular molar into two halves followed by removal of diseased root and its coronal portion, while retained the healthy portion of tooth segment, thus maintaining its integrity within the socket and the furcation area is made self-cleansable resulting in allow improved access for home care and plaque control with resultant bone formation.²

By post treatment approach, these teeth can be used as an individual unit or as an abutment to fix a prosthesis which can restore its masticatory function as well. Thus, a conservative approach preserve the tooth structure as much as possible and

therefore retain at least a part of tooth rather being getting extracted as a whole.³

This case report describes the treatment of endo-perio lesion, where the distal half of the mandibular left first molar had to be preserved and the untreatable mesial half of the tooth was extracted through hemisection procedure.⁴

Case Report

A 59-year-old male patient reported to the department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with the chief complaint of loose tooth and pain in his lower left back tooth region from last 2 months. Pain was dull and intermittent in nature, which aggravated during mastication. Patient gave medical history of hypertension since 13 years and he was on medication and dental history of R.C.T. i.r.t. 35, 1 year back (Fig.1&2).

In intraoral examination, tooth was tender on percussion and was grade I mobile. On probing, lower left mandibular first molar, a periodontal pocket of 8-10

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mm on buccal and mesial surface was found. Vitality test of #36 yielded no response.

Radiographic examination revealed grossly decayed mesial half, grade II furcation defect with loss of periodontal bone along with the mesial root as compared to distal root and periapical rarefaction present in both the roots of #36 (Fig.3). The periodontal support of distal root of 36 was good. On the basis of history, clinical and radiographic examination, a diagnosis of localized destruction of periodontal tissue and advanced endo-perio lesion with respect to tooth #36.

The treatment included extraction of 36 followed by placement of removable partial denture, fixed partial denture or implant but as the patient was unwilling to get the tooth extracted, a conservative approach was carried out which included the hemisection of mesial root of 36 followed by its prosthetic coverage. The prognosis of hemisection against extraction of tooth was discussed with patient.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2 Preoperative clinical view

Fig. 3 Preoperative Radiographic view

The treatment plan was explained to the patient and his informed consent was obtained. Oral prophylaxis was done out before commencement of the treatment procedure.

Armamentarium

Long, shank tapered fissure bur, extraction forcep, periosteal elevator, saline to remove bony chips, finishing diamond point, tissue forceps, needle holder, bone curette, 3-0mersilksuture material etc. (Fig-4).

Fig. 4 Armamentarium for Hemisection Procedure

Procedure

Endodontic Phase

Root canal treatment of 36 was done. After 2 weeks of obturation, hemisection procedure was carried out.

Surgical Phase

After application of local anesthesia, crevicular incision was made from second premolar region to second molar region. Full thickness mucoperiosteal flap was raised to provide access for proper visualization, instrumentation and minimal surgery.

After reflecting the flap, both curettage and debridement were done. After that, long shank tapered fissure carbide bur was used to make a vertical cut facio-lingually towards bifurcation area in #36 (fig-5).

Fig- 5 Vertical Cut i.r.t. 36

After completion of the sectioning, the mesial root along with its coronal part was luxated with elevators. The mesial half of the tooth was removed from the socket with an extraction forcep (Figure 6&7). The socket was irrigated adequately

with normal saline to remove bony chips. Granulation tissue was curetted out of the mesial socket using surgical curettes (Figure 8). Odontoplasty was done to remove the developmental ridges while the mesial aspect of the distal root was contoured for facilitating oral hygiene measures.

The extraction socket was sutured with 3-0 mer silk suture material and covered with a periodontal dressing i.e. Coe pack (Fig 9). A postoperative X-Ray was taken to evaluate the complete surgical procedure (fig-10).

Fig. 6

Fig. 7 Extracted Mesial Segment of Mandibular Left 1st Molar

Fig. 8. Removal of Granulation Tissue

Fig. 9 Suture Placed

Fig. 10 Postoperative Radiograph

Patient was recalled after one week for reevaluation. At this visit clinical examination revealed edema and inflammation was present at the extracted site. Irrigation with betadine solution was done and sutures were removed (Fig 11 & 12).

Fig. 11. Suture removed

Fig. 12. Follow up after 1 week (Clinical view)

At 1-month recall visit, patient was asymptomatic and healing of surgical site was found to be satisfactory (Fig-13).

Fig. 13. 1 Month follow up Radiograph

Tooth preparation for porcelain fused to metal crown was done using distal segment of mandibular first molar and second premolar as abutments (Fig-14). Impression was taken and die was fabricated and sent to laboratory for fabrication of prosthesis. After that final prosthesis was placed by using luting cements (Fig-15 and 16). Post cementation instructions regarding its maintenance were given to the patient.

Fig-14. Tooth Preparation i.r.t. 35 & Retained 36

Fig-15. Prepared prosthesis on a master cast

Fig-16. Cementation of prosthesis in 35 & 36

Discussion

Root amputation/hemisection is a useful alternative procedure to save those multi-rooted teeth which have been indicated for extraction. Before selecting a tooth for hemisection, patient's oral hygiene status, caries index and medical status should be considered. Also, accessibility of root furcation for easy separation as well as good bone support for the remaining root should be assessed.

In the present case, because of excessive destruction of the mesial root due to the external root resorption and fair amount of the distal root remaining with adequate bone support, hemisection was carried out with the removal of the mesial root and crown.⁵

Loss of posterior teeth may result in several undesirable sequelae such as mesial drifting, loss of arch length, and loss of masticatory function.⁶

The long-term success of hemisected molar depends on a number of interrelated factors: periodontal condition of tooth, root anatomy, maintenance therapy, endodontic and restorative therapy and the surgical procedure itself.⁷

From periodontal aspect, the amount of bone support and degree of furcation involvement are major determinants for case selection and prognosis. From endodontic point of view, factors such as inoperable canals, weakening of the lateral walls of the remaining roots during endodontic instrumentation or post preparation and poor post design are the causes of failure of resected molars.^{8,9}

Weine has given an insight on the specific indications where this procedure should be considered.¹⁰

1. Through and through furcation destruction.
2. Severe vertical bone loss involving only one root of multi-rooted teeth.
3. Unfavourable proximity of roots of adjacent teeth, preventing adequate hygiene maintenance in proximal areas.
4. Severe root exposure due to dehiscence.
5. Prosthetic failure of abutments with in as plint.
6. Vertical fracture of one root.
7. Perforation through the floor of the pulp chamber.

There are three following phases:

A. Endodontic Phase.

Endodontic treatment was performed first because in case, if the tooth cannot be treated endodontically or if there is an endodontic failure, the case will be contraindicated for hemisection.

B. Periodontic Phase.

Four critical factors in selecting molar for hemisection are following :

1. Root Divergence. Ideally the resected root should have generous root divergence, as close root proximity will make surgery difficult.
2. Root Form. Roots of mandibular molars show concavity, mostly on distal root. Therefore, odontoplasty should be performed to provide a proper contour.
3. Location of Furcation. Closer the furcation opening to the cemento-enamel junction, better the prognosis for retained root.
4. Remaining Root Attachment. is critical to evaluate; as cylindrical, ovoid, and long root serves as an excellent abutment.

Objectives

1. To facilitate maintenance.
2. To prevent further attachment loss.
3. To obliterate furcation defects as a periodontal maintenance problem.

C. Prosthodontic Phase.

When the tooth lose part of its root support, it will require a restoration to permit it to function independently or serve as an abutment for fixed partial denture or splint. Thus, restoration is required for function and stabilization of occlusion.¹¹

Park et al.¹² has also suggested that hemisection is a reliable treatment option for molars with questionable prognosis as it will maintain the teeth without detectable bone loss for along-term period, provided that the patient has optimal oral hygiene.

Saad et al.¹³ have also concluded that hemisection of a mandibular molar may be a suitable treatment option when the decay is restricted to one root and the other root is healthy and remaining portion of tooth can very well act as an abutment.

In the present case there was complete furcation involvement and the distal half of the tooth was sound. Thus considering these factors and patients financial constraint and time, hemisection was chosen as the treatment of choice.¹⁴ This case demonstrate shemi section as an alternative treatment to extraction of a whole tooth and salvation of healthy tooth

structure.^{15,16}

Conclusion

With advancements in endodontics, periodontics and restorative dentistry, hemisection can be considered as a predictable treatment option for a hopeless tooth. The key is the meticulous case selection and the treatment goal is to try and maintain what is present for restoration of the function. The prognosis for hemisection is the same as for routine endodontic procedures provided.

This case report demonstrated the treatment of periodontally involved tooth structure of #36 by multi disciplinary approach. The level of success of the hemisection procedure depends on the supporting bone of the remaining tooth, restorative treatment plan and oral hygiene care of the patient.

Thus hemisection has received acceptance as a conservative and dependable dental treatment which will help in more desire to retain long term natural teeth in oral cavity.

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